

Eco-friendly microwave enhanced synthesis of pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine as well as pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidine derivatives and studies of their antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : 7-[4'-(2'',5''-Dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-2-methyl-5-(substitutedphenyl)3(*H*)pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-4-one (4a-j) and 4-methyl-5-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-2-oxo-7-(substitutedphenyl)2(*H*)pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidin-8-carbonitrile (5a-j) have been synthesized by the reaction of 2-amino-6-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-4-(substitutedphenyl)pyridine-3-carbonitrile (3) with acetic anhydride and ethylacetoacetate respectively. These compounds have been screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against different microorganisms. The structures of novel synthesized compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral data.

Keywords : Pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine, pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidine, antibacterial, antifungal activity, microwave technique.

Introduction

The increasing importance of pyrimidine and its derivatives as intermediates for the synthesis of biologically active compounds has led to continuing development of new simple procedures for their synthesis. Pyrimidines and fused pyrimidines, being an integral part of DNA and RNA, play an essential role in several biological processes and have considerable chemical and pharmacological importance. Diverse biological properties have been shown to be associated with numerous fused pyrimidines, including analgesic¹, anti-inflammatory¹, antihypertensive, antipyretic, antiviral^{2,3}, antimycobacterial⁴, antihistamic⁵, antifungal⁶ and antimicrobial⁷ activity. Many of the pyrimidine derivatives are reported to possess potential CNS depressant properties⁸. Pyrimidine derivatives, a constituent unit of nucleobases⁹, are useful in drug discovery. Recently, it has been proved that pyrimidine and fused heterocyclic pyrimidine nucleus are potent antiviral agents.

The synthesis of pyridopyrimidine and their derivatives is of high interest in organic chemistry, because some are possessing biological and pharmacological activities. The pyridopyrimidine functionality has also been used for the development of biologically interesting molecules¹⁰. Earlier reported procedures for the synthesis of pyridopyrimidines typically involved a multistep-ap-

proach¹¹. Pyridopyrimidines were reported to be used as a cytotoxic agents and apoptosis inducers¹², adenosine kinase inhibitors^{13,14}, inhibitors of pneumocystis carinii, toxoplasma gondii and mycobacterium dihydrofolate reductase¹⁵ and as an anti-tumor¹⁶ agents.

Microwave irradiation is used for carrying out chemical transformations, which are pollution free, and eco-friendly^{17,18}. The basis of this technique of synthesis is the empirical observation that some organic reactions proceed much faster and with higher yields under microwave irradiation compared to conventional heating¹⁹.

Most organic reactions requiring heat have been heated using traditional heat transfer equipments such as oil baths, sand baths or heating mantles. These techniques are rather slow and create a temperature gradient within the sample. So, here we wish to report the synthesis of some novel 7-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-2-methyl-5-(substitutedphenyl)3(*H*)pyrido[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-4-one (4a-j) and 4-methyl-5-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-2-oxo-7-(substitutedphenyl)2(*H*)pyrido[1,2-*a*]pyrimidin-8-carbonitrile (5a-j) from 2-amino-6-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-4-(substitutedphenyl)pyridine-3-carbonitrile (3a-j) and using acetic anhydride and ethyl acetoacetate respectively by conventional and microwave assisted methods. The reaction carried out in (DMF + ethanol) using conventional method requires about 6 to 9

h, while microwave irradiation method requires only 4 to 6 min.

In conventional method, the yield is lower as compared to microwave irradiation, demonstrating the effect of microwave irradiation is not purely thermal. Microwave irradiation facilitates the polarization of the molecule under irradiation causing rapid reaction to occur. The synthetic route of above-mentioned compounds is shown in Scheme 1.

Results and discussion

The starting compound 2-amino-6-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-4-(substitutedphenyl)pyridine-3-carbonitrile (**3**) have been synthesized by refluxing 1-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-3-(substitutedphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**2**), malanonitrile and ammonium acetate. Further, it's reaction with acetic anhydride and ethyl acetoacetate gives compounds **4a-j** and **5a-j** respectively.

The structures were established through IR, ¹H NMR

Scheme 1

and Mass spectral data. In IR spectra of **4a-j**, significant bands were appeared at 1675 (C=O), 2870 (-CH₃), 3200 (-NH) and 3375 (-OH) cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra of these compounds revealed signals at δ ~ 7.9 (-NH) and ~ 5.93 (-OH) and beside the other signals in their expected positions. In IR spectra of **5a-j**, structure were proved by appearance of significant bands exhibited at 1670 (C=O), 2200 (-CN) and 3375 (-OH) cm⁻¹. In ¹H NMR spectra of these compounds structure was evident by appearance of signal at δ ~ 2.26 (-CH₃), ~ 5.93 (-OH) and other signals in their required positions.

Antimicrobial activity :

The newly synthesized compounds **4a-j** and **5a-j** were

screened for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram +ve), *P. Aeruginosa* (Gram +ve), and *Escherichia coli* (Gram -ve), and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined using Disk Diffusion method according to the standard procedure at three-test concentration, 128, 256 and 512 µg/ml. DMF was used as a blank and Streptomycin and Dithane M-45 were used as antibacterial and antifungal standards respectively. The screening results exhibited the MIC against the microorganisms in the range 128–512 µg/ml. Results are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Characterization of compounds

Compd.	R	Mol. formula (Mol. wt)	M.p. (°C)	Conventional method		Microwave method		N(%)	
				Time (h)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Yield (%)	Calcd.	Found
4a	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ (451.00)	160	6–7	68	5–6	80	8.84	8.81
4b	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ (451.00)	191	6–7	64	5–6	82	8.84	8.82
4c	-H	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ (421.00)	> 300	6–7	65	5–6	84	9.43	9.40
4d	2-Cl	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₃ (455.50)	> 300	6–7	60	5–6	75	8.76	8.75
4e	3-NO ₂	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₅ (466.00)	195	6–7	64	5–6	78	11.42	11.39
4f	2-OH	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ (437.00)	> 300	6–7	65	5–6	77	9.11	9.09
4g	4-OH	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ (437.00)	120	6–7	63	5–6	74	9.11	9.08
4h	4-COOH	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ (465.00)	178	6–7	68	5–6	76	8.58	8.55
4i	3,4-di-OCH ₃	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ (481.00)	168	6–7	62	5–6	80	8.31	8.29
4j	3-OH, 4-OCH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅ (467.00)	> 300	6–7	66	5–6	79	8.55	8.52
5a	3-OCH ₃	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ (475.00)	173	7–8	64	4–5	82	9.31	9.28
5b	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ (475.00)	221	7–8	62	4–5	79	9.31	9.30
5c	-H	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ (445.00)	205	7–8	66	4–5	80	9.97	9.94
5d	2-Cl	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₃ (478.50)	268	7–8	61	4–5	82	9.22	9.20

Table-1 (contd)

5e	3-NO ₂	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₅ (490 00)	203	7-8	68	4-5	78	12 01	11 98
5f	2-OH	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ (461 00)	254	7-8	65	4-5	80	9 61	9 58
5g	4-OH	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄ (461 00)	189	7-8	64	4-5	75	9 61	9 59
5h	4-COOH	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ (489 00)	210	7-8	68	4-5	78	9 03	9 00
5i	3,4-di-OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ (505 00)	200	7-8	63	4-5	77	8 73	8 70
5j	3-OH. 4-OCH ₃	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅ (491 00)	152	7-8	68	4-5	76	8 99	8 95

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of compounds 4a-j and 5a-j

Compd	Antibacterial activity									Antifungal activity		
	Gram +ve						Gram -ve			<i>C. albicans</i>		
	<i>E. coli</i>			<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			<i>S. aureus</i>					
	128 (µg/ml)	256 (µg/ml)	512 (µg/ml)	128 (µg/ml)	256 (µg/ml)	512 (µg/ml)	128 (µg/ml)	256 (µg/ml)	512 (µg/ml)	128 (µg/ml)	256 (µg/ml)	512 (µg/ml)
4a	-	++	+++	-	++	+++	-	++	+++	-	+	++
4b	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	+++	-	+	+
4c	-	++	+++	-	++	+++	-	++	++	-	-	++
4d	-	+	+++	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	+
4e	-	++	+++	-	++	++	-	++	++	-	+	++
4f	-	+	++	-	+	+++	-	+	++	-	-	++
4g	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	+++	-	-	+
4h	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	++
4i	-	++	++	-	+	+++	-	+	+++	-	+	+
4j	-	++	+++	-	+	++	-	+	+++	-	+	++
5a	+	++	+++	+	++	+++	-	++	+++	-	+	++
5b	+	++	+++	-	++	+++	-	++	+++	-	+	++
5c	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	+
5d	-	++	+++	+	++	+++	-	++	+++	-	+	+
5e	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	-	++
5f	-	+	++	-	+	++	-	++	++	-	-	++
5g	+	+	++	-	+	++	-	++	++	-	-	+
5h	+	+	+++	-	+	+++	-	+	++	-	+	++
5i	-	++	+++	-	++	++	-	++	+++	-	+	++
5j	-	+	+++	-	+	++	-	+	+++	-	+	+
Streptomycin	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	-	-
Dithane M-45	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	++++	++++

The inhibition diameter in mm (-) = <6 mm, (+) = 7-10 mm, (++) = 11-15 mm, (+++) = 16-21 mm, (++++) = 22-28 mm

Note

(4a-j)

Experimental

Reagents, instrumentation and measurements :

All reagents, solvents and catalyst were of good quality and used directly. All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC (0.5 mm thickness) using silica gel-G coated Al-plates (Merck) and spots were visualized by exposing the dry plates in iodine vapours.

Apparatus :

IR spectra (γ_{\max} , cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Shimadzu FT-IR spectrophotometer using KBr pallet method. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance-II 400 MHz NMR instrument, using $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvent and TMS as internal reference (chemical shifts in d , ppm). Mass spectra were performed on a Jeol-SX 102/DA/6000 spectrometer.

(5a-j)

The elemental analysis (C, H, N) of compounds were performed on a Carlo Erba-1108 elemental analyzer. Their results were found to be in good agreement with the calculated values. The microwave-assisted reactions were

carried out in a Q-Pro-M Modified Microwave Synthesis System. Here, these microwaves are generated by magnetron at a frequency of 2450 MHz having an output energy range of 100–500 W. This apparatus is well suited

for stringent reaction conditions, namely, anhydrous atmosphere, controlled temperature (using a fiber optic as an individual sensor for temperature control) and attachment of reflux condenser with constant stirring. The physical properties are summarized in Table 1.

Synthesis of 1-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-3-(substitutedphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (2) :

Conventional method :

A solution of 1-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-ethan-1-one (0.01 mol) in methanol and various substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) were taken and to it 5 ml 2% NaOH solution was added. The reaction mixture stirred for 6 h and then the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and acidified with conc. HCl. The solid product thus separated out, was filtered, dried and crystallized from ethanol.

Synthesis of 2-amino-6-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-4-(substitutedphenyl)pyridine-3-carbonitrile (3) :

A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol), malononitrile (0.01 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.08 mol) in mixture of ethanol + DMF (4 : 1) was refluxed for 5 to 6 h and then allowed to stand at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice with constant stirring. The solid, thus obtained, was filtered, washed with water, and recrystallized from DMF-ethanol (1 : 10).

Synthesis of 7-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-2-methyl-5-(substitutedphenyl)3(H)pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-one (4a-j) :

Conventional method :

A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (0.03 mol) and H₂SO₄ (0.5 mL) was heated under reflux for 4 h. The resulting residual mass was cooled, poured into crushed ice, filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol.

Microwave method :

A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (0.03 mole) and H₂SO₄ (0.5 mL) in DMF + ethanol was irradiated inside a "Q-Pro-M Modified Microwave" System for 5–6 min. After completion of reaction, mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice with constant stirring. The solid, thus obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol (1 : 10).

Synthesis of 4-methyl-5-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-2-oxo-7-(substitutedphenyl)2(H)pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-8-carbonitrile (5a-j) :

Conventional method :

A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.02 mol) was heated under reflux at 180 °C for 5 h. The oil obtained was washed with diluted NaOH solution and precipitated by adding ethanol. The solid so obtained was filtered and recrystallized from DMF-ethanol (1 : 10).

Microwave method :

A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.02 mol) in DMF + ethanol was irradiated inside a "Q-Pro-M Modified Microwave" System for 5-6 min. After completion of reaction, mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice with constant stirring. The solid, thus obtained, was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol (1 : 10).

Spectral data of 7-[4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl]-2-methyl-5-(2-chlorophenyl)3(H)pyrido[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-one (4d) : Brown powder, m.p. > 300 °C; IR [γ_{\max} , cm⁻¹, KBr] : 750 (-Cl), 1615 (C=N), 1669 (C=O), 2873 (-CH₃), 3215 (-NH), 3395 (-OH); ¹H NMR [400 MHz, δ , ppm, DMSO-*d*₆] : 2.270 (3H, s, -CH₃), 5.933 (2H, s, -OH), 7.951 (s, -NH pyrimidine ring), 6.842–8.120 (11H, m, Ar-H); M/S, *m/z* : 456 (M⁺), 458 (M+2), 273, 185, 160, 131, 116.

Spectral data of 4-methyl-5-(4'-(2'',5''-dihydroxyphenyl)phenyl)-2-oxo-7-(3-nitrophenyl)2(H)pyrido[1,2-a]pyrimidin-8-carbonitrile (5e) : Dark brown powder, m.p. 202–203 °C; IR [γ_{\max} , cm⁻¹, KBr] : 1555 (-NO₂), 1620 (C=N), 1690 (C=O), 2240 (-C=N), 2981 (-CH₃), 3410 (-OH); ¹H NMR [400 MHz, δ , ppm, DMSO-*d*₆] : 2.270 (3H, s, -CH₃), 5.940 (2H, s, -OH), 6.855–8.146 (12H, m, Ar-H); M/S, *m/z* : 490 (M⁺), 305, 183, 168, 155, 140, 129, 122, 109.

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